

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the seventh issue in 2023. I am very pleased to announce the journal's continued high Scopus CiteScore of 2.7 and Web of Science Impact Factor of 1.0 for 2022, indicating another scientifically successful year. On behalf of the J.UCS team, I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research contributions, the reviewers for their very helpful suggestions for improvements, and the consortium members for their financial support. Your commitment and dedicated work have contributed significantly to the long-lasting success of our journal.

As we want to secure the financial support also for the years to come, we are looking for institutions and libraries to financially support our diamond open access journal as consortium members, who will then benefit from the research community, international visibility, and the opportunity to manage special issues and focused topics within the journal. Please think about the possibility of such financial participation of your institution, we would be very grateful for any kind of support.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce six accepted papers from seven different countries and 20 involved authors.

Ana P. Allian, Leandro F. Silva, Edson Oliveira Jr and Elisa Y. Nakagawa from Brazil present VMTools-RA, a reference architecture that encompasses the knowledge and practice for developing and evolving variability tools. In a collaboration between researchers from the UK and Estonia, Vimal Dwivedi, Mubashar Iqbal, Alex Norta and Raimundas Matulevičius are focusing their research on the evaluation of a legally binding smart-contract language for blockchain applications. Monika, Seema Verma, and Pardeep Kumar from India discuss an intelligent vision-based decision-making system for the exploration of past aviation accidents and incidents, which is based on a visual query-based model capable of analyzing the major factors including flight phases, human factors, weather conditions, and faulty components in particular aircraft models. Luis Eduardo Ordoñez Palacios, Víctor Bucheli Guerrero and Hugo Ordoñez from Colombia present their research on integrating satellite imagery and meteorological data to estimate solar radiation applying and evaluating five machine learning models. In a collaboration between researchers from Palestine and Egypt, Muath Sabha, Thair Thahir, and Marwa M. Emam apply cooperative swarm intelligence algorithms to adaptive multilevel thresholding segmentation of COVID-19 CT scan images. Geovana Ramos Sousa Silva, Genaina Nunes Rodrigues and Edna Dias Canedo from Brazil introduce their work on a modeling strategy to design and verify chatbot conversational flows via the Uppaal model checking tool.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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